

IMPROVING THE TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS

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Annotation: In recent centuries, the negative impact of humans on the natural environment has also begun to undermine human health and economic sustainability. Perceptions of environmental disasters and the future of the world, views on the future environmental destiny is carried out with sustainable development of environmental competencies. Environmental education develops environmental competence of students.

Key words: eco-dependence, ecological consciousness, ecological culture, ecological behavior, competence, worldview, ecological values, ecological problem, ecological activity.

Pedagogy is not limited to the education and training of students of higher educational institutions, but serves as the main source of increasing their environmental knowledge, developing spiritual needs for the preservation and preservation of natural swamps. Therefore, instilling love for nature in the hearts of the younger generation depends on the knowledge of students about ecology.

As you know, the external and internal world of a person; buoy-Basti, appearance, clothing, behavior, purpose of life.thinking, dreams, aspirations, feelings depend on ecological, physical, spiritual, moral culture [5]. While food develops a person

physically and physiologically, ecological culture makes an important attempt to improve the relationship between man and nature.

Ecological culture is closely connected with moral culture, makes a person's inner world, his will energetic, faith whole, awakens conscience. Consequently, ecological culture is connected with the concepts of moral culture and represents a set of different knowledge about society and the essence of man. Environmental competence refers to the cumulative achievements achieved in social and spiritual life, such features as education, education, intelligence. Environmental competence does not arise in a person in a ready-made form. This is achieved only through continuous learning, training, acquisition of knowledge and skills, as well as education. The more ecological competence develops in a person, the more he knows what the ecology of man and nature is, he is looking for a way to live his life under a meaningful nature, at the same time his ecological competence develops and begins to approach nature fairly.

Specialists with high qualifications and communicative characteristics make up the human capital of society and serve as the basis and main reserve of a rapidly developing modern economy. At a time when the world community is at the epicenter of the development of the digital economy of information and communications, a professional can fully express himself in the field of his activity only when he is focused not only on limiting future specialists with knowledge, skills and abilities, but also on the content of general and professional competencies in them.

It provides for the development of environmental competence among future teachers on the basis of existing competencies through interdisciplinary integration of environmental competencies, structuring of environmental competencies based on a differential approach, the definition of environmental competence based on the qualification requirements of future specialists. The understanding of environmental competence in relation to personality-oriented and professional activities in the form of conscious activity is manifested in the following areas of life through situations in

which the student's personal capabilities and experience acquire a complex ecological nature

1. The world of knowledge. Environmental competence is formed through the application of knowledge, skills, skills acquired by a person in the learning process, in new and unforeseen situations when solving problems arising in the learning process, making necessary decisions in environmentally problematic situations.

2. The civil society layer. Ecological competence develops due to the fact that a person as a member of society fulfills civic duties and responsibilities related to the environment, uses natural resources rationally as a consumer, actively participates in environmental actions, mass environmental protection events.

3. In the social and labor layer, the degree of mastery of environmental competence increases due to the mastery of professional activity corresponding to a person's chosen specialty.

4. The layer of everyday life. In this layer, environmental competence is aimed at maintaining a healthy lifestyle without various bad habits, rational use of renewable and non-renewable natural resources, compliance with environmental safety in everyday life.

5. Cultural and educational layer. Environmental competence is formed on the basis of knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by an individual in the system of continuing education, through the use of mentally, physically, cultural, educational, mentally developing methods, activities

In order to develop environmental competence, future teachers conduct reflexive, facilitation, problem-educational and information-innovative activities aimed at the formation of leaders-leaders, giving the opportunity to apply knowledge, skills, basic and subject-specific competencies acquired in the educational process to solving environmental problems in independent life and professional activity, influencing the consciousness of students by means of modern information technologies. technologies,

and an electronic textbook, a visual tour, and non-standard tests were introduced as teaching tools.

The development of environmental competence among future teachers includes understanding and memorizing the information system (lecture), classification and characterization of information, discussion of personal views structured in the form of negotiations, organization of business games (practical lesson), understanding of the axiological content of information, orientation of the value system to social and professional tasks (lecture-conversational classes), formation of an emotional perception of a person in relation to information. From the student's life experience, the use of the Internet and additional resources (independent learning) is organized.

The development of environmental competence of future teachers is divided into several stages. The first stage is motivation. Students should consciously feel the need for acquired knowledge and clearly define goals and objectives. At the same time, students get acquainted with the main content of environmental activities, the initiative and the concept of "environmental competence", the science they have mastered is synthesized. The first step at this stage is the motivation of students. For this purpose, an environment was created for students to consciously understand environmental processes (videos about the environment, nature, crises).

The content of analytical pedagogical laboratories at this stage is that the design of life processes (life events that form life experience, process design, i.e. educational dialogues between a teacher and a student, the formation of the studied material as emerging stages of culture by bringing learning closer to everyday life, the formation of one's own "I" through awareness of life values and the ability to enter into a balanced relationship with the environment).

The second stage is reproductive and educational. Development of scientific environmental knowledge through practical experience. The substantiation of the experience of scientific ecological cognition directs knowledge, skills and abilities to

the level of competence with further consolidation. The process of mastering the algorithm of works

- identification of an urgent problem;
- choosing a theme for the design;
- putting forward task or ideological hypotheses;
- implementation of modeling;
- it is recommended to prepare and protect the presentation of the creative work.

The third stage is constructive. At this stage, students demonstrate their “methods”. At the constructive stage, the socio-psychological world of the individual is illuminated. The submitted project will be reworked creatively. In a group of students, the topics may be different, but the system-forming basis is unique. This stage also consists of several parts, namely: - determination of the studied aspect on topical issues (by means of associative means, images, videos, texts, etc.).k.) the scale of the problem and the degree of accuracy;

Acceleration of the process of problem-based learning with the help of information and innovative educational technologies; - students analyze and group the answers; - illustrate learning goals through a problem tree; - definition of the object and subject of project work, justification and proof of idea generation; - there was the formation of reflection and the transformation of knowledge into axiological values.

The fourth stage is the formation and development of environmental competence of the student's personality. The uniqueness of this stage is that the student's personality begins to feel integrity with the world in his worldview. At this stage, students have the opportunity to put into practice reflexive, informational, communicative, facilitation.

Linking the integrated education system with the educational system of environmental competence, the integration of all subject skills and knowledge independently and holistically acquired by students with other subjects in the education system on the issues of environmentally safe condition (movement, activity), human

health and safety contributed to the development of a holistic natural science worldview among students

Summing up, we can say that nature awakens a sense of Homeland in a person, encourages him to work and courage, brings up a lot of feelings. And much more. For a civilized spiritually mature person, the preservation of the nature of his homeland becomes an integral part of his life and activity.

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